

A General Synthesis of α -Unsaturated Acids from Malonic Acid.

Part I

By

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Malonic acid has previously been condensed with aliphatic and aromatic aldehydes with the formation of alkylidene- and arylidene-malonic acids (Ann. 218, 145, 169; Stuarts, J. C. S., 1886, 365; Ann. 253, 374). (The usual condensing agents employed in these cases are invariably glacial acetic acid or acetic anhydride.) In the case of aliphatic aldehydes the corresponding dicarboxylic acids, being very unstable, generally decompose under the experimental conditions into the corresponding α -unsaturated monocarboxylic acids and carbon dioxide. But in the case of aromatic aldehydes, such decomposition is not effected and they are isolated as unsaturated dicarboxylic acids with the general constitution of

These when heated much above their melting points, are slowly decomposed into the corresponding monocarboxylic acids with the elimination of carbon dioxide.

In the course of the following investigation it has been found that malonic acid easily condenses with aldehydes in presence of piperidine in pyridine solution to alkylidene- and arylidene-malonic acids, which under the influence of pyridine particularly on heating lose carbon dioxide with the greatest ease yielding α -unsaturated monocarboxylic acids in excellent yields. The

influence of pyridine in these cases is very interesting, as the corresponding dicarboxylic acids in their isolated conditions are not appreciably decomposed on heating to the boiling temperature of pyridine, *viz.*, 116°C. In pyridine solution, however, they get decomposed even at ordinary temperature though very slowly, and very rapidly at 100°C. The alkaline nature of pyridine has probably nothing to do in this connection as the dicarboxylic acids in caustic alkali solution do not eliminate carbon dioxide on heating, but are decomposed into the corresponding aldehydes of malonic acid.

Comparing with Perkin's method of synthesis of unsaturated acids from aldehydes, it has been found that the present method is superior to the former as it gives a much better yield of an exceedingly pure substance. The process is also much easier and quicker to carry out than Perkin's method. The only drawback of this process is that aromatic hydroxy-aldehydes either do not react or give a bad yield. This, however, can be remedied to a considerable extent by employing carbethoxy derivatives of these hydroxy-aldehydes in place of the parent substances. Even then the yield of the unsaturated acid is not quite so good as that obtained with non-hydroxy-aldehydes in this process.

It has been found that ketones also react with malonic acid by this process. Except in the case of acetone the yield of the corresponding unsaturated acid obtained is, however, far from satisfactory.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation with Aldehydes and Ketones.

General Procedure.

The aldehydes and ketones mentioned below were mixed with suitable quantities of malonic acid and pyridine and a few drops of piperidine and heated under

reflux for periods varying between one to six hours, except in the case of cinnamic aldehyde which required sixteen hours. After reaction the mixtures were poured into water and acidified with hydrochloric acid, when the products separated out as crystals. These were further purified by crystallisation and identified. In some cases, as mentioned below, the products were extracted, from the acidified aqueous mixture, with ether and crystallised from these ethereal solutions.

Condensation with Aldehydes.

(1) *Acetaldehyde*.—The product was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was shaken with sodium carbonate solution, and the aqueous solution separated. Crystals which separated on evaporating the ethereal solution melted at 72°C. Yield 75%. Identified to be crotonic acid.

(2) *Glyoxalic acid*.—The product crystallised from hot water. Sublimes at 200° without melting. Identified to be fumaric acid. Yield 1.8 gms. from a mixture of 10 gms. of glyoxalic acid and 10 gms. of malonic acid.

The filtrate after separating the above product from aqueous solution was shaken with ether. Long crystals were obtained from this solution by evaporation. M. P. 130°C. Identified to be maleic acid, yield 2.8 gms.

(3) *Benzaldehyde*.—Product crystallised from hot water was identified to be cinnamic acid. M. P. 133°C. Yield 90%.

(4) *p-Toluic Aldehyde*.—Product crystallised from dilute acetic acid was identified to be *p*-methyl cinnamic acid (Ber. 23, 1033) M. P. 198°C. Yield 87%.

(5) *Furfurol*.—Product which crystallised from hot water was identified to be furfuraerylic acid. M. P. 140°C. Yield 70%.

(6) *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde.—Product crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Identified to be *o*-nitrocinnamic acid. M. P. 236°. Yield 73%.

(7) *m*-Nitrobenzaldehyde.—Product crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Identified to be *m*-nitrocinnamic acid. M. P. 196°. Yield 90%.

(8) *p*-Nitrobenzaldehyde.—Product crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Identified as *p*-nitrocinnamic acid. M. P. 285°. Yield 82%

(9) Piperonal.—Product crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Identified as piperonyl acrylic acid (J. C. S., 1891, 59, 153). M. P. 232°C. Yield 76%.

(10) Anisaldehyde.—Crystallised from alcohol. Identified to be *p*-methoxycinnamic acid. M. P. 172°C. Yield 80%.

(11) *p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde.—The product was poured into water and acidified with acetic acid. Product was finally crystallised from alcohol. Identified as *p*-dimethylaminocinnamic acid. M. P. 216° (Monat. 29, 899). Yield 65%.

Found: N=7.1. $C_{11}H_{13}NO_2$ requires N=7.3%.

(12) *m*-Bromobenzaldehyde.—Product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid and identified to be *m*-bromocinnamic acid. M. P. 178°C. Yield 83%.

(13) Salicylaldehyde.—The product after acidification with HCl in water was steam-distilled to remove excess of salicylaldehyde. Product crystallised out from mother-liquor on cooling and was identified to be *o*-coumaric acid. M. P. 200°C. Coumarin was obtained on treating this with 85% sulphuric acid. Yield of coumaric acid 20%.

(14) Vanillin.—(Carbethoxyvanillin was used.) Precipitate was extracted with sodium carbonate solution and acidified. The precipitate thus obtained was dissolved in alcohol and crystallised by evaporation. Identified to be ferulic acid. M. P. 168°C. Yield 12%.

(15) *Protocatechuic Aldehyde*.—(Dicarbethoxy derivative was used.) Crystallised from alcohol. Identified as caffeic acid. M. P. 213°C. Yield 7%.

(16) *Cinnamic Aldehyde*.—Crystallised from acetic acid and identified to be cinnamylidene acetic acid (Perkin, J. C. S. 1877, 1, 403). M. P. 165°C. Yield 60%. If heated only for two hours the main product is cinnamylidene malonic acid (Stuart, J. C. S. 1886, 365). M. P. 208°C. Yield 70%. On boiling in pyridine solution the transformation to cinnamylidene acetic acid is quantitative.

Condensation with Ketones.—In the following cases the reaction mixture was allowed to stand at ordinary temperature for 24 hours and then heated for two hours. The ethereal extract from water was treated with sodium carbonate solution, separated from aqueous layer, treated with a little animal charcoal, filtered, dried and evaporated.

(1) *Acetone*.—Product identified to be $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacrylic acid. M. P. 69°C. Yield 60%.

(2) *Diethylketone*.—Product was a thick oil which distilled at 218°-220°C. Identified to be $\beta\beta$ -diethylacrylic acid. (Ber. 1. 519). Yield 35%.

(3) *Cyclohexanone*.—Product identified to be *Cyclohexylidene acetic acid* (Wallach, Ann., 353, 888). Yield rather bad, not exceeding 5% even under most favourable conditions.

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